

“Did they, though, ever / Take you in”:

Two Typescripts of W. H. Auden’s Poem “Joseph Weinheber
(1892-1945)”

The Musulin Auden Papers

“In Solitude, for Company”: W. H. Auden After 1940—the 1995 volume of the *Auden Studies* series edited by Katherine Bucknell and Nicholas Jenkins—includes Stella Musulin’s essay on “Auden in Kirchstetten”. The typescript of an unpublished earlier version of that essay, “The Years in Austria”, provides a more comprehensive account of the correspondence that informs much of Stella Musulin’s text, and that will be in the focus of this paper. A regular exchange of letters develops after the first meeting in 1959: “It was in 1958 that by chance I met Christiane Zimmer at Prielau, and she suggested I should call on Auden: ‘After all, he’s your neighbour now’”, that is, from the perspective of “Schloss Fridau, in Lower Austria, about half an hour’s drive from Kirchstetten” (4).

“The lack of a telephone accounts for much of my correspondence with Auden, or rather, because I have only scant records of what I wrote, for his letters to me, and especially for the telegrams”, Stella Musulin writes: those are “messages which mark the development of a cosy routine of coming and going between Schloss Fridau, my mother-in-law’s place where I have a flat, and Kirchstetten” — “‘We are here, where are you?’ or ‘Wednesday would suit perfectly’ and so on” (6). But among the “small heap of correspondence lying on the filing cabinet beside my desk” (6), there is also what the published essay from 1995 — “Auden in Kirchstetten” — defines as “working correspondence”:

A certain amount of Auden’s working correspondence with me has survived. By far the most valuable items are, to me, the typescripts of new poems with brief letters scribbled in the margins, one of which is the text of “Stark bewölkt”, on the back of which he wrote: “Overleaf a poem which I want to dedicate to you. Firstly because of its subject, secondly be-

cause it is written in an imitation of a medieval Welsh metre called a Cywydd". (211)

An amount of Auden's working correspondence with her has survived Stella Musulin's death in 1996; and the Musulin estate includes also other such letters-with-typescripts sent by W. H. Auden. Some of the "small heap of correspondence" is related to a long poem – twelve unrhymed stanzas of ten lines each – addressed to the Austrian poet Josef Weinheber:

It was part of his whole relationship with Lower Austria, his feeling for the landscape, for its history, for the history of the people who lived, or had lived there. Auden felt at home in Lower Austria and it satisfied him to live next door to the house where Weinheber had lived, a man for whom he apparently felt a remarkable empathy and a strange compassion. ... Weinheber had allowed himself to be wooed by the Nazis, but later on he rejected them and, finally, he committed suicide. (211)

For Stella Musulin, it is in his Weinheber poem that "Auden's interest in Weinheber" (211) coincides with an interest of Kirchstettens when "in Josef Weinheber they had had a local poet laureate before, and now, in Auden, they had one again" (208):

There is a prose translation of the poem to Weinheber, made by Auden and a German friend, which he sent to me for checking together with some amendments to stanza 3. As the poem was written to commemorate the death of Weinheber, the prose translation was for general information. "Herewith my effort", Auden wrote, "to do my Gemeindepflicht" (his civic duty). (211)

Footnote 9 in Stella Musulin's essay cites the source as "ALS, from Berlin-Dahlem, postmarked 23.12.64; the original typescript of the Weinheber poem and the prose translation are still in my possession" (211). They are still in the possession of the Musulin family; but

the citation conflates into one single communication what must have been three separate correspondences, and there is occasion for a footnote to the footnote: while the Musulin estate includes two letters with typescripts—one published recently (designated *ALS-b* below) and the other unpublished (here designated *TLS*)—which document Auden’s revision of the poem, there is a partly unpublished earlier letter (here designated *ALS-a*) whose prose text partly anticipates two lines in the Weinheber poem (210).

First Autograph Letter (*ALS-a*)

First, there is an ALS – Autograph Letter Signed – to Stella Musulin dated “Dec 23rd” from “Berlin-Dahlem | Hubertusbaderstrasse 43”. Stella Musulin relates the letter to her own previous letter to Auden: “I had been reading a paperback, *The Rise of the South African Reich* by Brian Bunting, and mentioned it in my letter with particular reference to torture” (210). In her essay, she quotes the first paragraph, as well as a passage from the second and third paragraphs of Auden’s reply which meditates on “those who wish to destroy”, and whose content she relates to the eighth stanza of the Weinheber poem:

Of course you’re right about the lib-labs’ ostrich-like attitude to those who wish to destroy them, but one cannot let one’s name be associated with shits. Torture is the iniquity which utterly bewilders me. I know something about the evil in my own heart and in the sort of people I meet, but I cannot conceive of myself or them torturing anybody. Where do the torturers come from? What class? Whom do they marry? (210)

Footnote 7 in Stella Musulin’s essay cites “ALS, from Berlin-Dahlem, 23 Dec. 1964.” *ALS-a* consists of one page 8.3 by 11.7 inches watermarked “NEUSIEDLER JAPAN POST”, and continues as transcribed – curly braces will henceforth indicate handwriting:

{~~Have you ever met one?~~ To what pubs do they go?
much love and best wishes for 1965
Wystan}

Typed Letter (TLS)

Elsewhere in the Musulin estate, there is an undated TLS— Typed Letter Signed— which includes a hand-written postscript as well as the full typescript of an unpublished version of the poem: it is in this letter, that Auden refers to the planned “ceremony” on the occasion “of the twentieth anniversary of Weinheber’s death”, in connection to which he describes the poem as an “effort to do my Gemeindepflicht.” The *TLS* consists of three pages 8.3 by 11.7 inches water-marked again “NEUSIEDLER JAPAN POST”, and is transcribed below— square brackets mark explanatory additions, the number sign (#) replaces typed or written letters deleted by Auden, and typographic peculiarities are preserved:

JOSEPH WEINHEBER
(1892-1945)

Reaching my gate a narrow
Lane from the village
Passes on into a wood:
When I walk that way
It seems becoming to stop [5]
And look through the fence
Of your garden where (under
The circs they had to)
They buried you like a loved
Old family dog. [10]

Categorised enemies
Twenty years ago,
Now next-door neighbors, we might
Have become good friends,
Sharing a common ambit [15]

And love of the word,
Over a golden Kremser
Had many a long
Language on syntax,commas,
Versification. [20]

Yes,yes,it has to be said:
Men of great damage
And malengine took you up.
Did they,though,ever
Take you in,who to Goebbels' [25]
Offer of culture
Countered In Ruah lassen!?
But the crowd prefers
A nasty stink and the young
Condemn you unread. [30]

What,had you ever heard of
Franz Jägerstätter,
The St.Radegund peasant
Who said his lonely
Nein to the Aryan State [35]
And was beheaded,
Would your heart,as Austrian,
As poet,have told you?
Good care,of course,was taken
You should hear nothing, [40]

Be unprepared for a day
That was bound to come,
A season of dread and tears
And dishevelment
When,transfixed by a nightmare, [45]
You destroyed yourself.
Retribution was ever
A bungler at it:

Dies alles ist furchtbar,hier
Nur Schweigen gemäss. (1) [50]

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Unmarked by me,unmourned for,
The hour of your death,
Unhailed by you the moment
When,providence-led,
I first beheld Kirchstetten [55]

On a pouring wet
October day in a year
That changed our Cosmos,
The annus mirabilis
When Parity fell. [60]

Already the realms that lost
Were properly warm
And over-eating,their crimes
The pedestrian
Private sort,those nuisances, [65]

Corpses and rubble,
Long carted away: for their raped
The shock was fading,
Their kidnapped physicists felt
No longer homesick. [70]

To-day we smile at weddings
Where bride and bridegroom
Were both born since the Shadow
Lifted,or rather
Moved elsewhere. Never as yet [75]

Has Earth been without
Her bad patch,some unplace with
Jobs for torturers
(In what bars are they welcome?
What girls marry them?), [80]

Or her nutritive surface
At peace all over.
No one,so far as we know,
Has ever been safe,
And so in secret regions [85]
Good family men
Keep eye,devoted as monks,
On apparatus
Inside which harmless matter
Turns homicidal. [90]

Here,though,I feel as at home
As you did: the same
Short-lived creatures re-utter
The same care-free songs,
Orchards cling to the regime [95]
They know,from April's
Rapid augment of color
Till boisterous Fall
When at each stammering gust
Apples thump the ground. [100]

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Looking across our valley
Where,hidden from view,
Sichelbach tottles westward
To join the Perschling,
Humanely modest in scale [105]
And mild in contour,
Conscious of grander neighbors
To bow to,mountains
Soaring behind me,ahead
A noble river, [110]

I would respect you also,
Neighbor and colleague,

For even my English ear
 Gets in your German
 The workmanship and the note [115]
 Of one who was graced
 To hear the viols playing
 On the impaled green,
 Committed thereafter den
Abgrund zu nennen. (2) [120]

- # 1) Quotation from W's poem Auf das Unabwendbare.
 2) Quotation from W's poem Kammermusik.

Dear Stella:

Kirchstetten is intending to have a ceremony in memory of the twentieth anniversary of Weinheber's death. Herewith my effort to do my Gemeindepflicht.
 love

{Wystan.

P.S. Expect to return K April 22nd. Do hope you will be around.}

A plausible date of the letter is indicated in the typescript of the earlier version of Stella Musulin's Auden essay. In "The Years in Austria", she writes,

By 20th March 1965 he had completed, typed out and sent off to me the long poem to Weinheber, with the verse:

Today we smile at weddings
 Where bride and bridegroom
 Were both born since the Shadow
 Lifted, or rather
 Moved elsewhere. Never as yet
 Has Earth been without
 Her bad patch, some unplace with
 Jobs for torturers.

(In what bars are they welcome?
What girls marry them?) (14-5)

Apart from the first word (“Today” instead of “To-day”) and the absent comma at the end of the stanza, the spelling and punctuation—leaving aside the addition of spaces after commas—conform to the *TLS* typescript, which would seem to date the undated *TLS* March 20, 1965. March 20, moreover, would seem to agree with the announced return to Kirchstetten on April 22. Elsewhere again in the estate, there is an empty envelope from “Berlin-Dahlem | Hubertusbaderstrasse 43 | Germany” postmarked “20.III.65”, which may have been the original container.

Second Autograph Letter (*ALS-b*)

Third, there is another *ALS* which includes a typescript of 31 lines of the poem, as well as handwritten indications of “a few slight changes in stanza 3” and the reference to “a prose translation made by me and a German friend” enclosed, together with the request to “check the translation for errors”; the letter is dated “Wednesday , Kirchstetten”. *ALS-b*, which is also reproduced in the 2014 collection of essays, *Silence Turned into Objects: W. H. Auden in Kirchstetten*, edited by Ricarda Denzer and Monika Seidl, consists of one unwatermarked page 8.3 by 11.7 inches, and is transcribed here:

JOSEPH WEINHEBER
(1892-1945)

Reaching my gate a narrow
Lane from the village
Passes on into a wood:
When I walk that way,
It seems befitting to stop [5]
And look through the fence
Of your garden where (under
The circs they had to)

They buried you like a loved
Old family dog. [10]

Categorised enemies
Twenty years ago,
Now next-door neighbors,we might
Have become good friends,
Sharing a common ambit [15]
And love of the word,
Over a golden Kremser
Had many a long
Language on syntax,commas,
Versification. [20]

Yes,yes,it has to be said:
Men of great damage
And malengine took you up.
{Rev |} Did they for long,though,
{ |} Take you in,who to Goebbel#s' [25]
Offer of culture
Countered In Ruah lassen!?
{rev. |} But Rag,Tag,Bobtail
{ |} Prefer a stink,and the young
Condemn you unread. [30]

What,had you ever heard of etc

{Wednesday , Kirchstetten

Dear Stella:

Many thanks for your letter. Will try to call you
to-day by phone.

I enclose a prose translation made by me and a German friend.

#Since the copy I sent you, # I have made a few slight
changes in stanza 3. (see above)

Could you check the translation for errors.

love
Wystan.}

While that translation is in a different place in the estate, the handwritten letter is in an envelope sent from “Berlin-Dahlem | Hubertusbaderstrasse 43 | Deutschland.”, postmarked “23.12.64”; the recto of the envelope is labelled with pencil, at top left, “Weinheber-Gedicht”: if that envelope originally contained *ALS-a*, *ALS-b* must have been misplaced therein. Elsewhere again, there is an empty envelope from Kirchstetten postmarked “28.IV.65”: April 28, 1965 was indeed a Wednesday – but, then again, so was December 23, 1964. The very least that can be said, with reasonable certainty, is that the *ALS-b* – in which Auden refers to the “the copy I sent you” in relation to which he has made the “changes in stanza 3” – must have succeeded the *TLS*.

Revisions

Footnote 9 in Stella Musulin’s 1995 essay, cites as one “ALS, from Berlin-Dahlem, postmarked 23.12.64” what in the Musulin Auden papers are three separate letters whose contents are interrelated in complex ways. Together with the partly unpublished *ALS-a*, a passage of which is quoted in “Auden in Kirchstetten”, the *TLS* and *ALS-b* outline the development of the poem from December 1964 to Spring 1965. The typescripts included in the *ALS-b* published in 2014 and the unpublished *TLS* – part of W. H. Auden’s “working correspondence” with Stella Musulin – document Auden’s revision of the Weinheber poem within the first third of 1965.

A collation of the two typescripts shows revisions in punctuation, syntax and lexis. In comparison with the *TLS*, the *ALS-b* version includes two changes in the first stanza – a comma is added at the end of line 4; in line 5, “becoming” becomes “befitting”:

When I walk that way	When I walk that way,
It seems becoming to stop	It seems befitting to stop
And look through the fence	And look through the fence
(<i>TLS</i> lines 4-6)	(<i>ALS-b</i> lines 4-6)

While the second stanza remains unrevised, it is the “changes in stanza 3” which Auden highlights in the *ALS-b* to Stella Musulin:

But the crowd prefers A nasty stink and the young Condemn you unread. (<i>TLS</i> 28-30)	But Rag,Tag,Bobtail Prefer a stink,and the young Condemn you unread. (<i>ALS-b</i> 28-30)
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The revision in line 24 modulates the question of whether “Men of great damage / And malengine” did “ever / Take you in” (22-5) into the different question if they did so “for long” (24):

Did they,though,ever Take you in,who to Goebbels' Offer of culture Countered <u>In Ruah lassen!</u> ? (<i>TLS</i> 24-7)	Did they for long,though, Take you in,who to Goebbel#s' Offer of culture Countered <u>In Ruah lassen!</u> ? (<i>ALS-b</i> 24-7)
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The *ALS-b* revisions correspond to the text in the first publication of the poem, “Joseph Weinheber / (1892-1945)”, in the July-1965 issue of *London Magazine*, with British-style “-our” spellings for words that Auden spelled with an American “-or”; the magazine’s house-style replaces “ised” with “ized” in “Categorised” (11) and omits the period after the abbreviation “St.” (33). The *London Magazine* text, which is close to the *ALS-b* typescript, varies from the earlier *TLS* version also outside the first three stanzas. In the published version, a comma is added in line 78, commas are deleted in lines 52 and 80, and a colon replaces the period in line 82 (“At peace all over:”). Rhythmically relevant is the deletion in line 38:

What Would your heart,as Austrian, As poet,have told you? (<i>TLS</i> 31-8)	What Would your heart, as Austrian, Poet, have told you? (<i>LondonMagazine</i> 31-8)
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The lexico-syntactic alterations that distinguish the *ALS-b* and *London Magazine* texts from the *TLS* typescript are consonant also with the text in the first book publication of the poem, "JOSEPH WEINHEBER / (1892-1945)", in Auden's *City without Walls* from 1969, where it is the first of "Five Occasional Poems". By comparison with the *London Magazine* version, commas are added in lines 1, 33, 52, 80, 85 and 98, and the commas deleted again in lines 4 and 78, in *City without Walls*. Colons replace the comma in line 84 ("has ever felt safe:") and the period in line 75 ("moved elsewhere: never as yet"); in line 82, a period replaces the colon ("at peace all over."). "Categorised" replaces "Categorized" (11) and American house style removes the hyphen from "Today" (71). Line-initial capitalization is removed apart from sentence beginnings, proper names and the German noun "Abgrund" (120). The word "cosmos" (58) is uncapitalized, whereas "Word" (16) and "Colleague" (112) are capitalized; "Neighbour" (112) keeps the uppercase letter despite line-initial decapitalization. The German-language "Kremser" (17) and the Latin "annus mirabilis" (59) are italicized; the river name "Perschling" is (mis)spelled "Perchling" (104). The Weinheber quotation "–in Ruah lossen?" (27), whose spelling more closely approximates a dialectal pronunciation of German "lassen" (*TLS* and *ALS-b*), loses the exclamation point. There is one lexical change – in line 84, being unsafe gives way to not feeling safe:

No one,so far as we know, Has ever been safe, (<i>TLS</i> 83-4)	No one, so far as we know, has ever felt safe: (<i>City without Walls</i> 83-4)
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A Report from the Auden House in Kirchstetten

W. H. Auden's Austrian house in Kirchstetten near Vienna is still an important "lieu de mémoire" related to his life and work – even more than forty years after his death. This fact is merely due to at least a handful Austrian people who held close contact to Auden and Chester Kallman during their lifetime. After his death they took strong efforts to collect Auden's Austrian papers and to establish a public memorial in the building which Chester Kallman gave to their housekeeper Josefa Strobl before he died in 1975.

The Community of Kirchstetten and the Department of Culture of the County of Lower Austria established a contract which included both the conservation of the Austrian Auden papers and the continuous use of the first floor of his Kirchstetten house as a personal museum in the late 1980s. Since the official opening in 1995, a steady flow of national and international visitors attended the place and witnessed the busy aura of Auden's „Cave of Making“, where he worked on his poems and essays during his summer stays from 1958 to 1973.